

MATHEMATICS

AN EFFICIENT METHOD FOR THE NUMERICAL SOLUTION OF FOURTH ORDER INITIAL VALUE PROBLEMS

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Abstract

In this paper, we propose an efficient numerical method to solve fourth order initial value problems. Analysis proves that the proposed method have at least quadratic convergence. Numerical results confirm the accuracy and efficiency of the proposed method.

Keywords: Initial Value Problems, Taylor series, Maximum Absolute Error, Approximation, Lipschitz condition.

1. Introduction

An efficient method for solving second order initial value problems has been proposed by P. K. Pandey and Archana Yadav in [6] and for third order initial value problems by the authors in [5].

In this paper, we study an effective numerical technique based on Taylor series approximation to solve fourth order initial value problems (IVPs) of the following type:

$$u^{IV} = f(x, u, u', u'', u'''), a \leq x \leq b, \quad (1.1)$$

subject to the initial conditions

$$u(a) = \alpha_0, u'(a) = \alpha_1, u''(a) = \alpha_2, u'''(a) = \alpha_3 \quad (1.2)$$

where the function f is continuous in $[a, b] \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}$.

We assume that f satisfies a Lipschitz condition in a convex domain D of $[a, b] \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}$ so that above problem 1.1 with 1.2 possesses a unique solution [1, 2, 3].

To find an approximation to the solution of the above problem, we discretize the domain $[a, b]$ into N equal subintervals each of size $h = \frac{b-a}{N}$:

$$a = x_0 < x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_{N-1} < x_N = b \quad (1.3)$$

where the nodes are given by $x_i = a + ih, i = 0, 1, \dots, N$.

We denote by $u(x)$, the true solution of the above problem in $[a, b]$ and by u_i, u'_i, u''_i, u'''_i the approximations to the true solution and its derivatives $u(x_i), u'(x_i), u''(x_i), u'''(x_i)$ respectively in

this order for each $i = 0, 1, \dots, N$. We also denote f_i for the approximate value of $f(x_i, u(x_i), u'(x_i), u''(x_i), u'''(x_i))$.

This article is arranged in the following order. In section 2, we derive the method and discuss its convergence. In section 3, we illustrate the method with examples.

2. The Derivation of the Scheme and Convergence Analysis

Choose and fix a real number a :

$a \neq -1$.

We define the scheme:

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{u_{i+1}} &= u_i + hu'_i + \frac{h^2}{2}u''_i + \frac{h^3}{6}u'''_i + c_1h^4u_i^{IV} + c_2h^5u_i^V \\ \overline{u'_{i+1}} &= u'_i + hu''_i + \frac{h^2}{2}u'''_i + \frac{h^3}{6}u_i^{IV} + c_1h^4u_i^V \\ \overline{u''_{i+1}} &= u''_i + hu'''_i + \frac{h^2}{2}u_i^{IV} + c_1h^3u_i^V \\ \overline{u'''_{i+1}} &= u'''_i + hu_i^{IV} + c_1h^2u_i^V \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

We find $a_0, b_0, c_0, d_0, c_1, c_2$ so that

$$u_{i+1} = a_0(\overline{u_{i+1}} + au_i) + b_0h(\overline{u'_{i+1}} + au'_i) + c_0h^2(\overline{u''_{i+1}} + au''_i) + d_0h^3(\overline{u'''_{i+1}} + au'''_i)$$

Using Taylor series on the left hand side

$$u_{i+1} = u_i + hu'_i + \frac{h^2}{2}u''_i + \frac{h^3}{3!}u'''_i + \frac{h^4}{4!}u_i^{IV} + \frac{h^5}{5!}u_i^V + O(h^6)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= a_0 \left(u_i + hu'_i + \frac{h^2}{2} u''_i + \frac{h^3}{6} u'''_i + c_1 h^4 u_i^{IV} + c_2 h^5 u_i^V + au_i \right) \\
&\quad + b_0 h \left(u'_i + hu''_i + \frac{h^2}{2} u'''_i + \frac{h^3}{6} u_i^{IV} + c_1 h^4 u_i^V + au'_i \right) \\
&\quad + c_0 h^2 \left(u''_i + hu'''_i + \frac{h^2}{2} u_i^{IV} + c_1 h^3 u_i^V + au''_i \right) \\
&\quad + d_0 h^3 (u'''_i + hu_i^{IV} + c_1 h^2 u_i^V + au'''_i)
\end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

Truncating the series and equating the corresponding coefficients of $u_i, hu'_i, h^2 u''_i, h^3 u'''_i, h^4 u_i^{IV}, h^5 u_i^V$ on both the sides, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
1 &= a_0(1+a) \\
1 &= a_0 + b_0(1+a) \\
\frac{1}{2} &= \frac{a_0}{2} + b_0 + c_0(1+a) \\
\frac{1}{6} &= \frac{a_0}{6} + \frac{b_0}{2} + c_0 + d_0(1+a) \\
\frac{1}{24} &= a_0 c_1 + \frac{b_0}{6} + \frac{c_0}{2} + d_0 \\
\frac{1}{120} &= a_0 c_2 + b_0 c_1 + c_0 c_1 + d_0 c_1
\end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

Solving these, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
a_0 &= \frac{1}{(1+a)} \\
b_0 &= \frac{a}{(1+a)^2} \\
c_0 &= \frac{a(a-1)}{2(1+a)^3} \\
d_0 &= \frac{a(a^2-4a+1)}{6(1+a)^4} \\
c_1 &= \frac{a^4-10a^3+14a^2+2a+1}{24(1+a)^3} \\
c_2 &= -\frac{22a^7-251a^6+97a^5+125a^4+100a^3-23a^2-11a-3}{360(1+a)^6}
\end{aligned} \tag{2.4}$$

We also get the expressions for the first, second and third derivatives:

$$\begin{aligned}
u'_{i+1} &= \left(\frac{\overline{u_{i+1}} - u_i}{24c_2 h} \right) + \left(\frac{24c_2 - 1}{24c_2} \right) u'_i + \left(\frac{48c_2 - 1}{48c_2} \right) hu''_i + \left(\frac{72c_2 - 1}{144c_2} \right) h^2 u'''_i + \left(\frac{4c_2 - c_1}{24c_2} \right) h^3 u_i^{IV} \\
u''_{i+1} &= \left(\frac{\overline{u'_{i+1}} - u'_i}{6c_1 h} \right) + \left(\frac{6c_1 - 1}{6c_1} \right) u''_i + \left(\frac{12c_1 - 1}{12c_1} \right) hu'''_i + \left(\frac{18c_1 - 1}{36c_1} \right) h^2 u_i^{IV} \\
u'''_{i+1} &= \left(\frac{\overline{u'''_{i+1}} - u'''_i}{2c_1 h} \right) + \left(\frac{2c_1 - 1}{2c_1} \right) u'''_i + \left(\frac{4c_1 - 1}{4c_1} \right) hu_i^{IV}
\end{aligned}$$

where $u_i^{IV} = f_i$.

If R_i denotes the remainder in the approximation at node i , then from above discussion we have

$$R_i = O(h^6).$$

Therefore, the accuracy of the above method is at least quadratic.

3. Numerical Illustrations

The following six problems illustrate the performance of our method. We compute the maximum absolute errors MAE, MAED1, MAED2 in the true solutions, its first and second derivatives $u(x), u'(x), u''(x)$, namely:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{MAE} &= \max_{1 \leq i \leq N} |u(x_i) - u_i| \\
\text{MAED1} &= \max_{1 \leq i \leq N} |u'(x_i) - u'_i| \\
\text{MAED2} &= \max_{1 \leq i \leq N} |u''(x_i) - u''_i| \\
\text{MAED3} &= \max_{1 \leq i \leq N} |u'''(x_i) - u'''_i|
\end{aligned}$$

All the computations were performed on Ubuntu 20.04.4 LTS linux operating system with IDLE 3.8.10 running Python version 3.8.10 on Intel Core[®] i5-9400 CPU @ 2.90GHz × 6 PC.

Example 1. Consider the fourth-order initial value problem:

$$u^{IV} = 12(u')^2 + 12uu'', 0 \leq x \leq 1$$

with the initial conditions:

$$u(0) = 1, u'(0) = -2, u''(0) = 6, u'''(0) = -24$$

with the exact solution

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{(1+x)^2}.$$

The output for $a = \frac{1}{2}$ is given below:

N	MAE	MAED1	MAED2	MAED3
256	0.00023970950451382422	0.0008648216360307992	0.00225840468932087	0.0037021091015531082
512	5.982651015087881e-05	0.00021575277277591232	0.0005632412917198626	0.0009233724670376642
1024	1.494378507291283e-05	5.388065621514393e-05	0.00014063586914719872	0.00023054351628482017
2048	3.7342291691055962e-06	1.3463768216648297e-05	3.5140921894327715e-05	5.760422733958048e-05

Example 2. Consider the fourth-order initial value problem:

$$u^{IV} = -u' - 4e^{-x}, 0 \leq x \leq 1$$

with the initial conditions:

$$u(0) = 0, u'(0) = 1, u''(0) = -2, u'''(0) = 3$$

with the exact solution

$$u(x) = xe^{-x}.$$

The output for $a = \frac{2}{5}$ is given below:

N	MAE	MAED1	MAED2	MAED3
256	5.07782070557905e-07	1.9225837056791274e-06	5.241934204647247e-06	8.475958695464136e-06
512	1.2714545172265446e-07	4.810618334961402e-07	1.3107540829948583e-06	2.1174836130066765e-06
1024	3.173316220905775e-08	1.2019330018038228e-07	3.277544385338338e-07	5.292859011074569e-07
2048	7.888418029899924e-09	2.99736465765539e-08	8.182726823902087e-08	1.321730801473464e-07

Example 3. Consider the fourth-order initial value problem:

$$u^{IV} = -4 \cos x + u, 0 \leq x \leq 1$$

with the initial conditions:

$$u(0) = 0, u'(0) = 0, u''(0) = 2, u'''(0) = 0$$

with the exact solution

$$u(x) = x \sin x.$$

The output for $a = \frac{1}{2}$ is given below:

N	MAE	MAED1	MAED2	MAED3
256	6.059861937801614e-07	2.3726911722032895e-06	6.807556253068947e-06	1.2082855353146016e-05
512	1.5178042078733966e-07	5.939416483080606e-07	1.702995872043811e-06	3.019631480416507e-06
1024	3.801529435687456e-08	1.4862909636370603e-07	4.259044633914133e-07	7.547607223656883e-07
2048	9.50230039098443e-09	3.7099023408870835e-08	1.0634909525242264e-07	1.8851668448505166e-07

Example 4. Consider the fourth-order initial value problem:

$$u^{IV} = 24u^5, 0 \leq x \leq 1$$

with the initial conditions:

$$u(0) = 1, u'(0) = -1, u''(0) = 2, u'''(0) = -6$$

with the exact solution

$$u(x) = \frac{1}{1+x}.$$

The output for $a = \frac{1}{2}$ is given below:

N	MAE	MAED1	MAED2	MAED3
256	3.12434808869555e-05	0.00010626888116294086	0.00024724704317630186	0.0003021831752841875
512	7.799656273788091e-06	2.6515978590990752e-05	6.166201796634074e-05	7.532371792307035e-05
1024	1.9483945974396732e-06	6.622357080932062e-06	1.5396774960679815e-05	1.88032057674703e-05
2048	4.867235900429812e-07	1.6544980299126877e-06	3.846811710089826e-06	4.697267051378962e-06

Example 5. Consider the fourth-order initial value problem:

$$u^{IV} = -4e^x \sin x, 0 \leq x \leq 1$$

with the initial conditions:

$$u(0) = 0, u'(0) = 1, u''(0) = 2, u'''(0) = 2$$

with the exact solution

$$u(x) = e^x \sin x.$$

The output for $a = \frac{1}{2}$ is given below:

N	MAE	MAED1	MAED2	MAED3
256	9.99910898968892e-07	4.130361320520137e-06	1.2933133346493264e-05	2.7246045575912703e-05
512	2.505632772376032e-07	1.0346073273659329e-06	3.237528902300113e-06	6.81208237440778e-06
1024	6.2869359496176e-08	2.5931127334288817e-07	8.098177088911029e-07	1.7027831056282139e-06
2048	1.570052088339935e-08	6.487729509174756e-08	2.0249710130926246e-07	4.257019761144676e-07

Example 6. Consider the fourth-order initial value problem:

$$u^{IV} = 4e^x(3 + 2x) + u, 0 \leq x \leq 1$$

with the initial conditions:

$$u(0) = 0, u'(0) = 0, u''(0) = 2, u'''(0) = 6$$

with the exact solution

$$u(x) = x^2 e^x.$$

The output for $a = \frac{1}{2}$ is given below:

N	MAE	MAED1	MAED2	MAED3
256	4.287940488012509e-06	1.859161943329468e-05	6.367776486371213e-05	0.0001640355317604758
512	1.0749753238670223e-06	4.658764012788197e-06	1.595006763821516e-05	4.1036406344119314e-05
1024	2.6924900131675145e-07	1.166706365296477e-06	3.9914350757896955e-06	1.026271385740074e-05
2048	6.733705149031266e-08	2.917741479535607e-07	9.98234828131217e-07	2.5661813722877014e-06

Example 7. Consider the fourth-order initial value problem:

$$u^{IV} = u - 8xcos x - 12 \sin x, 0 \leq x \leq 1$$

with the initial conditions:

$$u(0) = 0, u'(0) = -1, u''(0) = 0, u'''(0) = 7$$

with the exact solution

$$u(x) = (x^2 - 1) \sin x.$$

The output for $a = \frac{1}{2}$ is given below:

N	MAE	MAED1	MAED2	MAED3
256	8.668500844586244e-07	0.9960709314811149	1.6641355185864626e-05	4.7245480606195045e-05
512	2.1775315399446997e-07	0.9980411616543208	4.171866886171216e-06	1.1821233000253173e-05
1024	5.4437395932624075e-08	0.9990220080755576	1.0444202032111605e-06	2.9565572439160803e-06
2048	1.361527236406552e-08	0.9995113612579783	2.613367224846286e-07	7.395293688539084e-07

4. Conclusion

In this paper we have proposed a numerical method to solve fourth order initial value problems having at least quadratic convergence. We have given the derivation for the proposed scheme and estimated the error involved. We have also given several numerical examples which confirms our claim.

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